

SMART ERA

Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results v1/D7.2

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CSO	Civil Society Organization
DC	Dissemination and communication
DEC	Dissemination, exploitation and communication
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, ad Exploitation
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
MRS	Macro Regional Strategies
PCDE	Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results
SH	Stakeholder
SIPs	Smart Innovation Packages
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises

Executive Summary

The present **Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (PCDE)** of results outlines the integrated **CDE strategy** that will support SMART ERA's objectives in terms of impact maximization both during and after the project implementation period. Additional information for project partners can be found in the **Consortium Guidance** in the project repository.

Key Exploitable Results

KERs

Preliminary analysis of the proposal KERs giving insights into the **nature** of the results produced and their **operative implications** in SMART ERA

IPR

Preliminary assessment of **Intellectual Property (IP) scenarios**, monitored and updated throughout the project through constant dialogue with consortium partners

Stakeholders (SH) and key messages

Stakeholders

- Entrepreneurial local ecosystem
- Local authorities and agencies
- Research and Academia
- Technology and service providers
- Policy Makers and Regulatory agencies
- Civil Society
- Initiatives and Clusters
- Financial bodies
- Media

Key messages and payoff

Key messages

- Empowering rural communities for a sustainable future with SMART ERA
- The vision of a smarter, greener and innovative rural areas is coming to life with SMART ERA
- Leading rural economies towards resilience and vibrancy, SMART ERA will make the impact last!

Payoff

SMART ERA: your community, our future

Preliminary exploitation strategy

5 exploitation pathways were identified:

1. Knowledge transfer, policy advisory and replication
2. Technology upscaling and commercialisation
3. Pilot sustainability and service improvement
4. Academic and research exploitation
5. Third party exploitation

Key takeaways

- SMART ERA approach is towards open access results to empower rural areas fostering the **replication and sustainability** of the pilots
- **Innovative business models** are at the foundation of the replication processes in other areas

Communication & Dissemination (C&D)

Visual Identity

SMART ERA

Project logo

C&D channels

- Website: <https://smartera-project.eu/>

Landing page

- Social media and multipliers

C&D activities

- Social media
- Visual identity
- Brandbook
- Templates
- Landing page
- Newsletters
- Communication kit
- Journalistic articles
- Practice abstracts
- Press and news releases
- Video production
- Scientific publications
- Info-packs
- Policy briefs
- Best practices book

C&D activities focus on direct community engagement, targeted messaging, strategic use of social media, and partnerships with key SHs to effectively reach and involve rural communities

NEXT STEPS

The PCDE will be regularly updated throughout the project to reflect its progress and maturation. **The next release will be D7.5 at M24.**

1. Introduction: an integrated approach to Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication

1.1. Introduction

SMART ERA aims to address the challenges of depopulation in rural areas across Europe, primarily caused by the migration of young people, leading to an ageing population and structural issues such as limited job opportunities and deteriorating infrastructure. With the rise of digitalization and remote work options, there's an opportunity to reverse some of these migration trends and foster new sustainable growth models, leveraging concepts like multi-local living. SMART ERA intervenes precisely at this juncture.

Central to SMART ERA's approach is the effective integration and execution of Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities, synergistically aligned to achieve several objectives:

- Increasing project visibility and communicating its benefits to target groups and wider communities (C).
- Sharing knowledge and engaging key stakeholders with tailored strategies (D).
- Establishing pathways for the exploitation and sustainability of SMART ERA's outcomes (E).

The PCDE embodies an impact-oriented and holistic approach, aiming to generate impacts through awareness, acceptance of innovative approaches, and the uptake and scaling of project results beyond its duration.

The PCDE methodically identifies key exploitable results (KERs) and stakeholder groups, facilitating targeted actions across different geographical levels and timeframes. Communication efforts commence early in the project, engaging relevant stakeholders such as local rural communities, policy makers, investors and SMEs. Networking plays a vital role in leveraging synergies with other projects and partnerships fostering resilience in rural areas.

Monitoring and evaluation activities, utilising proprietary methodologies developed by ICONS, continuously assess the strategy's impacts and effectiveness, ensuring iterative refinement throughout the project lifecycle. The exploitation model encompasses all result types and pathways and is structured in three steps:

1. **Setting the scene:** Identifying Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and initial exploitation pathways.
2. **Shaping the strategy:** Developing a detailed plan to accelerate the adoption and replication of results.

3. **Involving enablers:** Implementing targeted dissemination activities to enhance uptake and replication potential. Insights from stakeholder interactions will feed back into refining the strategy.

This three-step approach maximises the impact and sustainability of SMART ERA's outcomes.

The ultimate objective is to make it easier to adopt and support the SMART ERA results by stakeholders, extending beyond the project's lifespan. Updated strategies will be documented in D7.4 "Exploitation mapping report" (M18), ensuring continued relevance and effectiveness. Through the implementation of a robust CDE strategy, stakeholders are expected to endorse and utilise SMART ERA results, contributing to lasting positive change in European rural areas.

Some paragraphs in this document refer to the [Consortium Guidance Note](#) for more detailed information on certain sections. The Consortium Guidance Note, created by ICONS, complements and facilitates the understanding of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (WP7) by the project partners. The document is accessible via a password provided to consortium and the Project Officer.

1.2. Objectives and approach to dissemination, communication and exploitation

Ensuring an effective DEC of project developments and its outcomes is pivotal to promote rural resilience through collaborative development of smart solutions. This endeavour aims to cultivate and disseminate knowledge, reducing hesitancy within the rural sector and enhancing public perception of the SMART ERA's Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs). Our approach prioritises impact, focusing on:

- Raising awareness among rural communities on the transition towards positive change.
- Promoting smart innovation in rural areas, thereby fostering the adoption of solutions and informing the development of robust policy frameworks.
- Ensuring the sustainability and practicality of project outcomes.

This initiative commences with an analysis of the needs addressed by our efforts and the anticipated outcomes within SMART ERA:

Table 1 Addressed needs and expected outcomes

Specific needs	Outcomes
Enhance resilience and minimise vulnerabilities within rural regions.	Develop a comprehensive methodology for smart rural transition, including a Smartness Assessment method and new datasets on rural socio-economic dynamics.
Enable rural communities to drive innovation across sectors that directly impact their daily lives.	Engage rural communities in co-designing innovative solutions tailored to their needs, facilitated by a Co-design toolkit, sustained by gamification-based methods to enhance the participatory processes.

Address rural depopulation and its associated challenges, such as an ageing population, limited job opportunities, infrastructure degradation, and reduced service availability.	Customise and integrate technological solutions into six SIPs for pilot rural areas, accompanied by a SMART ERA data dashboard.
Advocate for innovative, sustainable growth models that prioritise environmental consciousness and community well-being.	Validate SMART ERA methods and solutions in pilot locations and transfer successful models to four follower regions, ensuring tested SIPs for rural areas.
Facilitate the integration of digitalization and remote work opportunities to counteract rural depopulation trends, fostering renewed interest in rural living.	Extract insights to enhance national and EU policies through tailored policy recommendations and a Policy toolkit.
Implement strategies to harness multi-local living trends, promoting sustainable and innovative growth models that accommodate diverse lifestyles and preferences within rural communities.	Execute a robust dissemination strategy and promote macro-regional networking, including a comparative study on smart villages and a Strategy for EU-level adoption of project innovative solutions.

1.3. Enhancing local communication through community engagement

Effective communication lies at the heart of successful community engagement within the SMART ERA project. We recognize that local communication strategies play a pivotal role in fostering meaningful connections, building trust, and empowering rural communities to actively participate in the project's initiatives. Apart from the structured approaches outlined in our communication, dissemination and engagement strategy presented in this deliverable (D7.2), we emphasize the importance of deploying tailored communication strategies that resonate with the unique characteristics and preferences of each pilot site.

Local communication serves as a bridge between the project consortium and the diverse stakeholders within rural communities. It ensures that project objectives, activities, and opportunities for involvement are communicated clearly and effectively, reaching individuals across different age groups, cultural backgrounds, and socio-economic statuses. Through localized communication channels such as community newspapers, radio broadcasts, and face-to-face interactions, we aim to cultivate a sense of ownership and belonging among community members, inspiring them to contribute their insights, ideas, and aspirations to the SMART ERA project.

Furthermore, local communication strategies facilitate the co-creation of knowledge and solutions by fostering dialogue, collaboration, and mutual learning among stakeholders. By actively soliciting feedback, sharing project updates, and celebrating successes, we nurture a culture of transparency and accountability, reinforcing the notion that the SMART ERA project is a collective endeavour driven by the aspirations and needs of the communities it serves.

In essence, local communication serves as a catalyst for community engagement, amplifying the impact of our efforts to promote smart and sustainable development in rural areas. By prioritising meaningful interactions, listening attentively to local voices, and adapting our communication strategies to fit the context of each pilot site, we endeavour to

build strong partnerships, nurture inclusive decision-making processes, and empower rural communities to chart their own paths towards a brighter future.

For this purpose, local DEC desks for each of the 6 pilot territories will be established to ensure the implementation of the DEC strategy at local/regional/national levels. These desks will serve as focal points for coordinating communication efforts, disseminating information, and facilitating dialogue between the project team and local stakeholders. By establishing dedicated desks within each pilot territory, we aim to enhance the localization of our communication strategies, ensuring that they are tailored to the specific contexts and needs of each community.

2. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

2.1. Preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identification

The table below lists the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identified during the proposal phase of the SMART ERA project. This list will be revised and updated throughout the 48-month duration of the project based on its implementation and developments. SMART ERA's KERs will be published on the Horizon Results Platform, with varying levels of detail depending on their confidentiality.

Table 2 SMART ERA's Key Exploitable Results

KERs	Type	Preliminary holders
KER 1 - Rural smartness assessment methodology	Methodology data, indicators and analyses to assess the smartness of EU rural areas	UOULU, WP2 partners
KER 2 - Co-design and motivational toolkit for rural innovation	Methodology/framework	FBK, WP3 partners
KER 3 - Novel technological solutions and data dashboard	Software, data	WP2, WP4 and WP5 contributing partners
KER 4 - Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs)	Integrated framework & methodologies	ENG, WP3/WP4 and WP5 partners
KER 5 - Policy recommendations & toolkit	Recommendations	AEIDL, WP6 partners
KER 6 - Innovative Business Models	Models	All partners
KER 7 - Analysis of smart villages and replication strategies	Advancement in knowledge, recommendations	W7 partners

While these KERs are diverse in nature, they collectively aim to enhance rural development through innovative tools, technologies, and strategies. By addressing key areas such as smart assessment tools, social innovations, and digital solutions, SMART ERA proposes a comprehensive framework for improving rural resilience and sustainability across Europe.

Each KER will be individually considered in the exploitation process. Below, a brief description is provided for each KER:

KER 1 - Rural Smartness Assessment Methodology, Tools and Data

This KER involves developing a comprehensive methodology to assess the smartness of rural areas. The approach is multi-dimensional, incorporating quantitative and qualitative methods to evaluate various aspects of rural life including mobility, governance, economy, environment, living conditions, and population dynamics. The methodology aims to help rural areas identify their smart transition needs and prioritise feasible innovations.

KER 2 – Co-design and Motivational Toolkit for Rural Innovation

This KER focuses on creating methods and tools for co-design and motivation that encourage active participation in rural innovation. The toolkit will include gamification-based methods to foster sustained engagement in the co-design processes, supporting the development of SIPs. These methods will enhance collaboration among stakeholders and promote behavioural change initiatives during the pilot implementation of innovations.

KER 3 - Novel Technological Solutions and Data Dashboard

This KER aims to establish a methodology for data integration and interoperability tailored to rural communities, ensuring data privacy and sovereignty. It involves developing a data dashboard for rural smartness assessment to aggregate and visualize pre-existing datasets, providing valuable insights tailored to each pilot region's needs. Additionally, it supports the adaptation and testing of all the new technological solutions to be integrated in the SIPs, focusing on seamless integration with local data sources and alignment with the specific requirements of rural areas. This setup facilitates data-driven decision-making and enhances community engagement in rural development initiatives.

KER 4 - Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs)

SIPs are integrated sets of innovative solutions both of digital and non-digital nature, tailored to address specific challenges faced by rural communities. These packages are developed through a co-design process that ensures they are adapted to local needs and are sustainable over time. SIPs aim for instance to improve access to services, enhance mobility, and ensure equitable resource distribution in rural areas.

KER 5 - Policy Recommendations & Toolkit

This result consists of a set of policy recommendations and a toolkit designed to inform and guide policy-making at various levels. The toolkit will include guidelines and tools that support the creation and implementation of policies aimed at fostering rural innovation and smart transition strategies through a community-led approach.

KER 6 - Innovative Business Models

This KER develops new business models that are integral to the sustainability of the SIPs. These models are designed to be innovative, replicable, and scalable, ensuring that they can be adopted not only in the pilot regions but also in other rural areas. The business models will focus on creating value propositions that are attractive to local stakeholders and can drive widespread adoption of smart innovations.

KER 7 - Analysis of Smart Villages and Replication Strategies

This involves a comprehensive analysis of smart villages, focusing on identifying successful strategies and practices that can be replicated in other rural areas. The KER aims to develop a systematic approach to understanding how smart solutions can be scaled and adapted to different rural contexts, supporting the broader application of the project's outcomes across Europe.

2.1.1. IP Assessment and IPR Management

SMART ERA adopts an open approach to sharing knowledge, stimulating innovation in rural areas. A preliminary Intellectual Property (IP) analysis was carried out at the proposal stage and will be updated throughout the project. An assessment of IP background and foreground ownership will be performed for consensus on exploiting joint results post-project and implementing effective IPR measures.

The general approach in SMART ERA is to publish all KERs as open access and open data, thus fostering sharing of knowledge and innovation in rural areas. However, specific IP measures such as copyright protection for publications and software solutions made by third parties will be put in place to ensure proper protection.

This approach ensures effective IP management and protection, supporting the sustainability and impact of SMART ERA's innovations while creating value and knowledge resources for the whole community.

2.2. Target audiences & key stakeholders

Project stakeholders encompass individuals, organizations, and businesses with a vested interest in SMART ERA and its tools and frameworks. These stakeholders can either influence or be impacted by the project's outcomes, applications, and performance.

A thorough stakeholder mapping is essential for developing an effective dissemination strategy and supporting a viable exploitation plan. Identifying and understanding the needs and priorities of project stakeholders enables to design an engagement strategy that supports result exploitation and involves relevant external parties, both during and after the project's execution.

This section provides an initial identification of the relevant actors in SMART ERA. Further analysis and prioritisation of stakeholders will be presented in later releases of the Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation of Results (D7.5).

2.2.1. Preliminary stakeholder identification

In SMART ERA, identifying key project stakeholders is closely connected to understanding the results (e.g., technologies, models, tools, frameworks, advancements in knowledge) that will be delivered, and how partners plan to leverage them post-project through individual and joint exploitation strategies. Based on the scope, objectives, and KERs of SMART ERA, a total of 8 stakeholder macro-groups have been identified, as presented in the table below:

Table 3 Project preliminary identified stakeholders

Macro Categories	Stakeholders
Entrepreneurial local ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs and startups • Local businesses • Local service providers (public and private) • Local cooperatives • Local business associations
Local authorities and agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional institutions • Municipalities • Local authorities in other regions • Regional development agencies • Other local agencies
Research and Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities • RTOs • Think tanks and policy research organisations
Technology and service providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consulting companies • Software and Smart solutions providers • Technology providers and developers • Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)
Policy Makers and Regulatory agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International policy makers • EU institutions • National governments • Regulatory agencies (environment, agriculture, data protection)
Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural citizens and tourists • General public • NGOs • CSOs
Initiatives and Clusters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU funded projects and initiatives • Digital Innovation Hubs and associations
Financial bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU funding agencies • Other public and private investors
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journalists and international/local media

2.2.2. Stakeholder profiling

This section provides a description of the identified stakeholder macro-groups and sub-groups presented in the above table along with their operational context and expected main interests in SMART ERA and its key results.

Entrepreneurial Local Ecosystem

This category of stakeholders includes various entities that are integral to the economic and social fabric of rural areas. This category includes SMEs and start-ups, local businesses, service providers (both public and private), cooperatives, and business associations. These stakeholders are central for the implementation and actual sustainability of SMART ERA

innovations. They could be mainly interested in enhancing business operations, improving service offering, and fostering sustainable local development through advanced technologies and innovative business models provided by the project.

The following sub-categories are identified:

- **SMEs and Startups:** small and emerging businesses drive local innovation and economic growth. They could be interested in SMART ERA's tools and methodologies to enhance their operations, expand market opportunities, and improve service delivery.
- **Local Businesses:** include retail, agriculture, and service-oriented enterprises that form the backbone of rural economies. They could adopt SMART ERA solutions to increase efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance customer engagement.
- **Local Service Providers:** deliver essential services such as healthcare, education, and utilities. They could be interested in integrating SMART ERA innovations to improve the quality and accessibility of their services.
- **Local Cooperatives:** member-owned organisations support various community needs, from agriculture to finance. They could be interested in the innovation and general benefits brought by SMART ERA in the rural economic ecosystem.
- **Local Business Associations:** represent the collective interests of businesses in rural areas. They are focused on advocating for the adoption of SMART ERA policies and innovations to drive regional economic development and support their members' growth.

Local Authorities and Agencies

This category includes regional institutions, municipalities, regional development agencies, and other local agencies responsible for governance and development in rural areas. These stakeholders are essential for the spread of the project results, playing a key role in the carrying on of replication activities. Their main interest is in the innovations and socioeconomic benefits SMART ERA could bring to rural areas under their administration, furthermore they could leverage policy recommendations and toolkits to enhance regional planning, improving public services, and engaging communities in the smart transition processes fostered by SMART ERA.

The following sub-categories are identified:

- **Regional Institutions:** these governmental bodies at the regional level are responsible for planning and development. They may benefit from the innovations brought in the region and could be interested in using SMART ERA's policy recommendations and toolkits to enhance regional development strategies and implement smart innovations.
- **Municipalities:** these local entities manage towns and cities. They may replicate and implement SMART ERA solutions to their settings, seeking to improve governance, public services, and community engagement, driving local smart transitions.

- **Local authorities in other regions:** include regions not initially involved in SMART ERA that could be interested in the project's outcomes. They may participate in future funding opportunities and seek to replicate the proposed solutions in their areas, thereby expanding the project's impact and fostering wider adoption of smart rural innovations.
- **Regional Development Agencies:** focus on economic growth and development within specific regions. They could aim to leverage SMART ERA's outcomes to stimulate innovation, attract investments, and support sustainable development initiatives.
- **Other Local Agencies:** include various administrative and service-oriented bodies at the local level, such as local health boards and agricultural agencies. They are interested in adopting SMART ERA methodologies and tools, particularly those implemented in the SIPs, to improve their operations and contribute to community well-being.

Research and Academia

This category includes universities, RTOs, and think tanks or policy research organisations. These stakeholders are key to advancing knowledge and innovation. Their interest in SMART ERA is driven by the opportunity to utilise project findings for academic research, and scientific publications. They could aim to apply SMART ERA methodologies, datasets and tools in further research to promote technological and social innovations in rural areas.

The following sub-categories are identified:

- **Universities:** higher education institutions engage in teaching and research. They are keen to incorporate SMART ERA findings into academic curricula, providing resources for PhD grants and courses thus advancing research in rural development and innovation.
- **Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs):** conduct applied research and development to support innovation across industries. They seek to apply SMART ERA methodologies in their projects to drive technological advancements and social innovations in rural areas.
- **Think Tanks and Policy Research Organisations:** focus on policy analysis and research to inform decision-making. They are interested in using SMART ERA's insights to develop policy recommendations and propose solutions to rural development challenges.

Technology and Service Providers

This category includes consulting companies, software and smart solutions providers, and technology developers at both local and EU level. These stakeholders are crucial for the deployment and/or refinement of SMART ERA's technological solutions, potentially participating in the project itself being applicant for the 1st Open Call. They can benefit from the knowledge produced to enhance their service offering targeting markets similar to the SMART ERA ones and facilitating replication of the solutions in other scenarios.

The following sub-categories are identified:

- **Consulting companies:** provide expert advice to businesses, organisations, and public authorities. They could be interested in leveraging SMART ERA's methodologies and findings to update their service offering, thus being able to support local communities' growth.
- **Software and Smart Solutions providers:** are responsible for the development of solutions to be integrated in the SIPs offering. They seek to adopt and adapt SMART ERA's innovations to create new products, software and services, enhancing their technological capabilities and potentially expanding their business in rural areas.
- **Technology providers and developers:** focus on creating and supplying technological solutions. They are providers of technological components as the ones included in the SIPs, they could be interested in updating their offering based on the needs outlined in SMART ERA for rural communities.

Policy Makers and Regulatory Agencies

This category encompasses international policy makers, EU institutions, national governments, and regulatory agencies focused on areas such as environment, agriculture, and data protection. These stakeholders shape the regulatory and operational frameworks within which SMART ERA operates. Their primary interest is in adopting the project's policy recommendations to drive rural development initiatives, align with best practices, and ensure compliance with regulatory standards.

The following sub-categories are identified:

- **International Policy Makers:** these entities influence policy across countries. They are interested in adopting SMART ERA's policy recommendations to support global rural development initiatives.
- **EU Institutions:** include the European Commission and European Parliament. They aim to integrate SMART ERA outcomes into EU-wide policies and funding programs to promote rural innovation. Examples of relevant institutions for SMART ERA could be DG AGRI, DG REGIO, European Committee of the Regions (CoR).
- **National Governments:** seek to align national policies with SMART ERA recommendations to enhance rural development and smart transition in rural areas.
- **Regulatory Agencies:** these agencies as the European Environment Agency, European Data Protection Board and many national and local agencies oversee specific sectors like environment, agriculture, and data protection. They are focused on ensuring SMART ERA's solutions comply with regulatory standards and contribute to sustainable development.

Civil Society

This category includes rural citizens, tourists, the general public, NGOs, and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). These stakeholders represent the broader community interests and are both beneficiaries and contributors to SMART ERA's success. Their interest revolves around the improved quality of life, enhanced services, and increased opportunities that SMART ERA solutions bring to rural areas.

The following sub-categories are identified:

- **Rural Citizens and tourists:** are the primary beneficiaries of SMART ERA's innovations. They are interested in improved services, enhanced quality of life, and increased opportunities in rural areas.
- **General Public:** broad society that has interested in requalification of rural areas. They support innovations that contribute to societal well-being and sustainable development.
- **NGOs:** work on various social, environmental, and economic issues. They are interested in SMART ERA to address rural development challenges and promote sustainable practices.
- **Civil Society Organisations (CSOs):** represent the interests of communities and advocate for societal change. They aim to ensure that rural voices are heard in decision-making processes and support community-driven initiatives.

Initiatives and Clusters

This category includes EU-funded projects and other initiatives, including Digital Innovation Hub (DIHs), the EU Macro-Regional Strategies (MRs) and various relevant networks and associations aimed at fostering innovation and development in rural areas. These stakeholders are important for knowledge exchange and collaborative efforts. Their interest in SMART ERA is driven by the potential to share resources, best practices, and synergize efforts to achieve common goals in rural development.

Examples of relevant projects included in the same call are RURACTIVE, FUTURAL, AURORAL, dRURAL, NATURELAB, RESONATE. Relevant EU-clusters for networking possibilities in SMART ERA could be PREPARE – Partnership for Rural Development, the Rural Smart Communities and the Smart Villages Portal. Other project SHs that will act as multipliers enabling the success of the C&D strategies are DIHs and other associations including EUHubs4Data, Rural DIH Network, Pact 4 Skills, EP Intergroup RUMRA and Smart villages, EURADA.

Furthermore, networking activities will be carried on between the EU MRS for the Alpine area (EUSALP), Baltic Sea (EUSBSR), Adriatic-Ionian (EUSAIR) and Danube Regions (EUSDR) thus strengthening their rural communities' capacity to effectively address socio-economic and environmental challenges using smart and sustainable solutions.

Financial Bodies

This category includes EU funding agencies and other public and private investors that provide financial support for rural development projects. These stakeholders are crucial for the implementation and scaling of SMART ERA solutions providing financial support for projects aligned with EU objectives. They are interested in funding SMART ERA initiatives that demonstrate potential for impactful rural development. Examples include the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and private actors as venture capitals or local investors.

Media

This category includes journalists and media organisations, including non-traditional media outlets, such as social media independent content creators (acting as 'local heroes') at both international and local levels that cover developments and innovations in rural areas. These stakeholders play a critical role in disseminating information about SMART ERA's progress, outcomes, and impacts.

2.3. Key messages at general and stakeholder level

Addressing the diverse range of targets within SMART ERA requires the development of a set of core messages that effectively communicate the project's objectives. By crafting tailored messages with specific keywords for different target audiences, we increase the project's resonance and potential for impactful outcomes.

The following tables provide an overview of the SMART ERA's key messages, **at both the project and target levels**. The messages were drafted starting from the inputs collected during a workshop session among project's partners held at the project's Kick-off Meeting in Trento.

Table 4 Key messages at the project level

Key Messages at the project level
Empowering rural communities for a sustainable future with SMART ERA
The vision of a smarter, greener and innovative rural areas is coming to life with SMART ERA
Leading rural economies towards resilience and vibrancy, SMART ERA will make the impact last!

Table 5 Key messages at the target level

Target	Key Message
Local Rural Ecosystem	SMART ERA empowers you to transform our villages into thriving, sustainable communities for generations to come.
	Turning local challenges into growth opportunities in rural areas.

Local authorities and agencies	Unlocking new market opportunities in rural areas through SMART ERA-driven innovations. Co-creating smart solutions with rural communities through impactful collaborations with SMART ERA.
Research and Academia	Informing the academic community with best practices and lessons from SMART ERA initiatives.
Technology and service providers	Driving rural innovation and digitalisation with SMART ERA technology solutions. Developing smart and sustainable rural ecosystems with SMART ERA Smart Innovation Packages.
Civil Society	Join SMART ERA to mobilise citizen engagement for a vibrant, sustainable rural future.
Policy Makers and Regulatory Agencies	Use SMART ERA insights to make policy decisions that reflect rural realities for impactful development. Leverage SMART ERA's innovative solutions to boost your rural development strategies.
Initiatives and Clusters	Strengthening collaboration and knowledge exchange among rural stakeholders through SMART ERA cluster networks.
Financial Bodies	Mitigate risks and maximise benefits by supporting SMART ERA project, driving sustainable rural development.
Media	Showcase community-driven innovation in shaping the future of rural landscapes with SMART ERA.

For a full view of all key messages generated with inputs by all partners during a workshop coordinated by ICONS, please refer to the [Consortium Guidance Note](#).

2.3.1. A tailored approach to dissemination and communication

The project will develop a PCDE articulated upon the following stages: engage, produce, share and exchange.

Figure 1 DEC stages

Communication and dissemination play a fundamental role in the “share”, “exchange” and “engage” stages. The dissemination efforts of the project aim to share its findings with the scientific community, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. The overarching goal is to support progress in scientific research, application of technology, and the development of policies based on evidence, all geared towards fostering long term impact.

Conversely, communication efforts enhance the project's public visibility and the dissemination of its outcomes. Utilising accessible language, these endeavours aim to pique public interest in the project's subject matter and highlight the anticipated long-term benefits that SMART ERA is poised to deliver to rural people's lives.

Table 6 Difference between dissemination and communication

	Dissemination	Communication
Objectives	Public disclosure of scientific and technical results	Promotion of the project and its benefits
Audience	Professional target groups, such as scientific communities, industry stakeholders, policy makers, etc.	General public, including EU citizens, civil society
Tone of voice	Scientific/technical language	Non-specialised/layman's terms
Channels	Papers in peer-review journals, scientific conferences, sector events, the web, newsletters, etc.	The web, social networks, journalistic articles, TV channels, radio, etc.

In sync with communication and dissemination efforts, exploitation endeavours will focus on laying the groundwork for applying scientific findings and technological innovations throughout and beyond the project's conclusion.

The following table illustrates how the project's dissemination and communication strategies will address each stakeholder category identified through the stakeholder mapping exercises.

Table 7 DC tailored to SMART ERA's stakeholders

Stakeholders	Dissemination formats	Communication channels	How DC supports exploitation
Policy Makers and Decision Makers	Leaflet, sector events, webinars, project presentations, info-packs, policy briefs, practice abstracts, videos, press and news releases, journalistic articles, video interviews	Website, social media, newsletter, sister projects' website, media multipliers, AEIDL's network and channels	Policy makers will be showcased as facilitators in SMART ERA's solutions for advancing towards sustainable rural development, tackling depopulation issues, and promoting resilience

Scientific Community and Academia	Leaflet, scientific and tech publications, sector events, webinars, project presentations, videos, press and news releases, best practices book, EIP-AGRI practice abstracts	Website, social media, newsletter, sister projects' websites, scientific journals	Scientific papers generated by SMART ERA will fortify the credibility the solutions like the SIPs in rural areas, offering robust scientific evidence accessible to interested stakeholders
SMEs, Industry and Service Providers	Leaflet, scientific and tech publications, sector events, webinars, info-packs and policy briefs, best practices book	Website, social media, newsletter	Dissemination materials tailored for SMART ERA will encapsulate the expertise of the project, emphasising replicability across various sectors
Multipliers, Media	Press and news releases, journalistic articles	Media multipliers	For media and multipliers, SMART ERA aims to enhance awareness of fostering resilience in rural areas, where depopulation is increasingly prevalent
Clusters	Leaflet, sector events, webinars, project presentation, info-packs and factsheets, videos, press and news releases	Website, social media, newsletters, sister projects' website	SMART ERA stakeholders will be offered the project's newsletter for broader outreach, fostering mutual expertise exchange and collaboration. Exclusive webinars will provide early access to results for their members
Local Rural Networks	Videos, press and news releases, journalistic articles, video interviews	Website, social media, multipliers	SMART ERA will address public perceptions of the solutions brought thanks to the SIPs
Civil society	Leaflet, info-packs and factsheets, videos, press and news releases, journalistic articles, best practices book	Website, social media, multipliers	The tone of voice in the communication targeted to them will be reassuring and will put an emphasis on the importance of rural areas
Public and Private Investors	Leaflet, project presentations, info-packs and factsheets, practice abstracts, videos, press and news releases	Website, social media, newsletter, sister project's website	SMART ERA will showcase the investment potential in sustainable rural development through its dissemination materials, encouraging investors to support innovative solutions

City Administration Actors	Leaflet, sector events, webinars, project presentations, info-packs, policy briefs videos, press and news releases	Website, social media, newsletter, sister project's website	SMART ERA will provide insights and evidence-based recommendations to and a toolkit to help them implement policies and initiatives that support rural resilience and sustainable development
Technology and Service Providers	Leaflet, scientific and tech publications, sector events, webinars, info-packs and policy briefs, factsheets	Website, social media, newsletter, tech publication	SMART ERA will tailor dissemination materials to highlight the opportunities for technology and service providers in implementing smart solutions in rural areas
Local Businesses	Leaflet, info-packs, factsheets videos, press and news releases, journalistic articles.	Website, social media, media multipliers	SMART ERA DC will emphasise the importance of rural areas for local businesses and promote opportunities for sustainable growth and collaboration within these communities

2.4. Dissemination & Communication channels

Table 8 Dissemination and communication channels at the target level

Channel	Description	Target
Website	The project website will be used to showcase details about the project, its objectives, challenges, and results. It will act as the primary communication channel between the consortium and SMART ERA target audiences; it is also the source of information about the six pilot regions involved and will offer updates on their local activities.	ALL
Landing page	The landing page is a preliminary version of the project website. This was put up online in M2, prior to the launch of the website. It contained an overview of the project and direct contacts to SMART ERA coordinator and communication partner	ALL
Social networks (X and LinkedIn)	These will be used to actively engage with the online community of the project's followers. This will be done by informing them about the progress made by SMART ERA and by inviting them to participate in a dialogue on the different topics/issues addressed by the project	ALL
Newsletter	It is released on a six-monthly basis to inform about the progress made by the project. It is structured upon a summary of the key events, journalistic articles, news or press releases issued by the project. Sister projects, partnerships and clusters	Local rural communities; EU partnerships; Industries and SMEs;

	will be offered a space in the SMART ERA newsletter	associations, clusters and membership organisations; education and research, scientific community; policy makers; media
Media multipliers	These are external platforms that republish the journalistic articles, relevant news and press releases written by SMART ERA	General public; policy makers; rural communities; media
SMART ERA online community	The project's online community (SMART ERA community on Discord) has been launched by FBC as one of the communication and dissemination channels - this will target all types of project stakeholders and will act as a space to discuss, interact and share knowledge, news, comments around the project and the open calls.	ALL

2.5. Dissemination & Communication materials, formats, and editorial contents

2.5.1. Formats

In SMART ERA, ICONS will manage the creation of content-specific dissemination and communication formats, ensuring their distribution through appropriate channels to maximise awareness, acceptance, and uptake. The project will develop the following materials and formats:

Table 9 Dissemination and communication materials and formats

Materia/Format	Description	Target
Communication Kit	The SMART ERA communication kit will entail a leaflet, roll-up, PowerPoint template and presentation video. Communication materials will be distributed both online (as downloadable materials on the website), and offline (to be displayed at workshops, exhibitions and external events attended by the partners). The materials' design will be consistent with the project's visual identity. The kit will be ready in August 2024 (M8).	ALL
Scientific publications	With support from ICONS, technical partners will produce scientific articles and papers to be published in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. Such scientific publications will present the cutting-edge results from SMART ERA.	Scientific community and academia, universities
Info-packs	Info-packs will present results in a concise manner. They aim to provide essential details about a particular topic, product, service, or event.	EU institutions, policymakers, researchers, project partners

Policy briefs	Policy briefs can be a highly effective formats for disseminating technical information and influencing policy decisions.	Policy makers and regulatory agencies, national governments, local governments, EU policy advisors, researchers
EIP AGRI Practice Abstracts	Practice abstracts serve as a valuable resource for farmers, policymakers, researchers, and practitioners, offering insights into successful agricultural innovations and inspiring further experimentation and adoption.	Policy makers, EU initiatives, farmers, foresters, rural communities and their representatives
Best practices book	SMART ERA will publish a best practices book, drawing on project achievements to offer valuable insights for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers. By sharing successful approaches and lessons learned, the project aims to inspire innovation and collaboration in the field.	Policy makers, researchers, project partners, industry professionals, service providers

2.5.2. Editorial contents

Table 10 Editorial contents

Editorial content	Description	Target
Journalistic articles	Independent articles and interviews with project experts and external stakeholders will be produced by professional journalists and distributed to online media, thematic portals, and other information outlets.	General public, local rural ecosystem, media
Press and news releases	These materials serve to inform the community about key project achievements, milestones, and upcoming events. Additionally, they will provide valuable insights into innovations relevant to smart communities, serving an informational purpose.	General public, policy makers, local business associations, initiatives and clusters, policy research organisations, media
Video production	SMART ERA videos will communicate the project in an easy and engaging way. Their format will be suitable for online distribution, although they may also be used to present the project at sector events.	General public, rural citizens and tourists, policy makers, European partnerships, associations, clusters, media

Regular monitoring of outreach efforts will enable us to continually refine the content of our communication materials, enhancing their impact over time.

2.6. Clustering, synergies, and events attendance

SMART ERA partners will engage in networking events to enhance project visibility and collaboration within the stakeholder community. They will establish synergies with EU-funded projects like FUTURAL and RURACTIVE, aiming for cross-fertilisation. Specifically, SMART ERA will cluster with projects funded under HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-02, to explore opportunities for organising joint workshops and disseminating research results. Collaboration with fellow projects will be highlighted on the website. Specifically, the project website will feature a dedicated section on clustering, listing the Macro Regional Strategies (MRS) involved in the project (EUSALP, EUSBSR, EUSDR and EUSAIR) and fellow projects RURACTIVE and FUTURAL with their logos, descriptions, and links to their websites.

Webinars will be organised towards the end of the project addressing early adopters to showcase the results and benefits linked to the SMART ERA solutions. The following timeline has been drafted with the organised/planned events for SMART ERA. The partner SAB, responsible for Task 7.5 "EU Macro-regional networking", is conducting these activities in coordination with the EU Macro Regional Strategies other representative in the consortium (BIF, WIEN, GODC), with the aim to enhance project visibility and dissemination across their respective networks. Interactive webinars and/or online workshops will be organised in collaboration with sister projects and experts from multiple disciplines. Such events will become an opportunity for sharing the wealth of valuable information on smart innovation in rural areas. During the first and second open call, dedicated webinars for potential applicants will be organized by FundingBox, with support from other partners. These online sessions will aim to introduce the open call rules, and guidelines and answer the questions from applicants.

Towards the end of the project, webinars will be organised by SAB, addressing early adopters to showcase the results and benefits linked to the SMART ERA solutions. Moreover, SMART ERA will participate in the dissemination event for the open call promotion.

Webinars and events will be organised during the project's lifetime; the following timeline has been drafted with the organised/planned events where SMART ERA will be presented. The table is constantly updated by the consortium with new upcoming opportunities and invitations to showcase the project and its results.

Table 11 Timeline events M1-M31

When	What	Who
M2	Study visit - CEEPUS – Central European Exchange Program for University Studies, Tourism and Agriculture Sustainable Alliances	TORS
M2	Agrotourism as a logistical support to the sustainability of the natural and cultural heritage of Slovenia and the Republic of Srpska	TORS
M2	TAIEX workshop Event on EU policies and best practices in rural tourism in the context of rural development	SFTH
M3	Workshop on EU policies and best practices in rural tourism in the context of rural development	TORS, SFTH

M3	Smart Community Meeting	FBK, POLI, SAB
M3	Final Conference of the Smart Rural 27 project	FBK
M4	CODECS webinar - Sustainable Digitalisation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	FBK
M4	Innovative solutions and a new model governance for sustainable mobility	UL
M6	Macro-regional & Sea Basin Strategies Days 2024	SAB
M6	Jazz Under the Stars Festival	DPA
M9	Mediterranean coast and MRS Week 2024	SAB
M10	Finalisation of comparative analysis on MRS	SAB
M18	Danube annual forum	SAB
M23	EUSALP Annual forum	SAB
M28	1st call for follower regions in the MRS territory	SAB
M30	Strategy for replication in EU macro-regions	SAB
M30-36	1 informative Webinar with Q&A session per open call	FBA
M31	2nd call for follower regions in the MRS territory	SAB

Table 12 Clustering, synergies and events accountability

Accountability	<p>FBK will lead T7.4 "EU Clustering activities" as coordinator and manage the clustering activities with all relevant EU projects and initiatives. SAB will lead T7.5 "EU macro-regional networking", exploiting its role in EUSALP and its strong relations with the other MRS. FBC will attend dissemination events.</p> <p>ICONS will be responsible for keeping track of all the events in which representatives of the SMART ERA partnership will participate and support with communication activities.</p>
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2.7. Management of communication, dissemination and exploitation

2.7.1. Responsibility in the consortium

To ensure effective EU-wide communication, the DEC Exploitation Leader (ICONS) must collaborate closely with the consortium. Strong synergy exists between project dissemination, local activities, and stakeholder engagement. Full cooperation from all team members is vital, as outlined in the [Consortium Guidance Note](#).

2.7.2. Stakeholder database

The stakeholder mapping, outlined in Chapter 2.1, initiates the creation of a stakeholder database, crucial for dissemination efforts, especially as tangible project results emerge in the second year. This dynamic database, GDPR-compliant, includes stakeholder type,

geographical reach, relevant KERs, preferred dissemination channels, and responsible partner details. Partners populate the database by identifying stakeholder organisations aligned with SMART ERA's KERs, subsequently engaging directly with them for dissemination. Task leaders, supported by ICONS, identify key features or results for targeted stakeholder communication, ensuring effective outreach throughout the project lifecycle.

2.8. Monitoring

2.8.1. ICONS' monitoring process

Throughout SMART ERA's duration, the impact of its DC products will be continually assessed by monitoring engagement with target audiences.

Online media outreach will be quantified using automated tools and indexes, explained in detail in the [Consortium Guidance Note](#).

2.8.2. Timeline

The timeline outlines key activities for WP7, spanning from project inception to M24 when the Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results will be updated with a second version of the deliverable. Initial months are dedicated to establishing the project's visual identity, social media presence, website, and outreach materials. In the same period, preliminary identification of SMART ERA KERs and stakeholder groups is conducted based on the project proposal and partner input.

Beyond the listed activities, biannual project newsletters will be produced, timed for optimal newsworthiness. Social media engagement is ongoing, fostering community growth within the SMART ERA consortium. Targeted communication campaigns are planned for significant events such as the Earth Day and the International Day of Rural Women. Press releases will be issued at project milestones, events, and notable achievements, and can be found on the [News section of the website](#).

Table 13 Timeline D&C M1-M24

When	What	Who
M2	Set up of social media accounts and visual identity design	ICONS
M2	Set up of the official project's hashtag: #SMARTERAeu	ICONS
M2	Brandbook, .ppt and deliverable templates	ICONS
M2	Landing page	ICONS
M5	Website	ICONS
M5	D7.1 SMART ERA website	ICONS
M6	Preliminary stakeholder mapping	ICONS
M6	Online community launch	FBC
M6	Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of results v1	ICONS

M6	First newsletter	ICONS
M8	Communication kit (presentation video, roll-up, leaflet)	ICONS
M9/10	Exploitation webinar	ICONS
M12	Second newsletter	ICONS
M10-15	Journalistic article #1	ICONS
M18	Dissemination of the open calls	ICONS, FBC
M18	Practice abstracts – batch 1	ICONS
M18	Third newsletter	ICONS
M18	Exploitation mapping report	ICONS
M24	Fourth newsletter	ICONS
M24	Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results v2	ICONS
M24	Report on C&D activities including impact analysis v1	ICONS

2.9. The project’s visual identity

An appealing and consistent visual identity is crucial for effectively engaging stakeholders and enhancing SMART ERA's influence and impact. The project logo was developed based on the SMART ERA brand personality exercise, emphasising the key features, characteristics, and elements that project partners wish to convey in their communications. The notions and sources of inspiration underlying the SMART ERA logo are: people, smart, rural areas, innovation, rural communities, home. The logo, meticulously crafted by ICONS design team, embodies the essence of transforming rural areas into vibrant, smart communities. It visually integrates elements that symbolise the fusion of technology and tradition of rural areas, highlighting the central role of innovation in enhancing the quality of life in these regions. The imagery of a house represents the concept of home and the strong sense of community, while the subtle incorporation of digital motifs reflects the technological advancements that drive this transformation. The choice of colours and shapes is deliberate, evoking a sense of warmth, connectivity, and progress. This visual identity, complemented by our evocative payoff "your community, our future" in all the pilot regions languages, underscores our commitment to fostering sustainable development and a brighter future for rural communities, emphasising that their growth and well-being are at the heart of our mission. Once the project's visual identity was established, ICONS created the official Word and PowerPoint templates for the project.

Figure 2 SMART ERA's logo

For more details about the project’s brandbook and visual identity, please refer to the [Consortium Guidance Note](#).

3. Exploitation strategy

3.1. Preliminary Exploitation Strategies

The SMART ERA consortium is committed to an impact-driven approach to ensure the sustainability and practical use of the project's outputs. Developing an exploitation strategy early in the project provides a framework to guide activities and decisions towards achieving the set goals. This strategy aligns with the general purpose of SMART ERA, fostering rural ecosystem development and replication of the pilots' initiatives, therefore broadening the impact of the measures implemented.

This section will focus on presenting the **preliminary exploitation pathways** identified for SMART ERA, specifically:

1. Knowledge transfer, policy advisory and replication
2. Technology upscaling and commercialisation
3. Pilot sustainability and service improvement
4. Academic and research exploitation
5. Third party exploitation

SMART ERA's exploitation strategy will be continuously updated and refined throughout the project.

3.1.1. Knowledge transfer, policy advisory and replication

This exploitation pillar focuses on ensuring that SMART ERA's outputs are effectively communicated, adopted, and replicated across various regions in Europe. To achieve this a comprehensive strategy has been initially outlined, the commitment of all the partners involved will be key to the actual success of the project.

The main objectives of this exploitation pathway are to:

- Facilitate the transfer of knowledge and best practices developed in SMART ERA;
- Provide policy advisory services to influence local, national, and European policy frameworks;
- Support the replication and scaling of successful SMART ERA solutions across the EU.

Policy advisory

Relevant SMART ERA partners will be the main drivers for the networking activities with policy makers at macro-regional level, having a deep understanding of policies and governance frameworks supporting rural development, thus ultimately supporting the replication of SMART ERA solutions and pilots.

To do so they will leverage results such as the rural smartness assessment methodology, tools and data to craft relevant policy recommendations and the interactive toolkit for policy makers, available in open access, to advise future policy making activities. Furthermore, fundamental for the success of the project will be the targeted dissemination of results to relevant EU policy network as CAP Network, EIP-AGRI, the European Evaluation Helpdesk, the Rural Pact and other actions of the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, the Rural, Mountainous and Remote Areas intergroup of the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee, European Committee of the Regions, thus enabling the actual usage of the knowledge and tools generated in the project.

Knowledge transfer (already before project's end)

There will be organised workshops and networking events for local communities, municipalities, and pilots' participants to foster cross pilot contamination and collaborative learning thus sharing relevant experiences and practices of the implemented solutions. Community activators will lead these efforts, focusing on transferring knowledge about SMART ERA solutions, implementation strategies, and best practices. These continuative efforts, that will endure also in the post-project phase, will empower local stakeholders with the skills and knowledge needed to adopt and implement and maintain over time SMART ERA solutions.

Pilot replication and scaling

The ultimate goal in SMART ERA is to provide all the instruments necessary for replicating and upscaling the solutions implemented in the pilot regions. To do so, the activities listed above are propedeutical and act as the base ground for setting effective strategies and involve more rural regions in the application of the solutions proposed.

Fundamental to this will be, within the Work Package dedicated to co-design (WP3), the development of innovative Business Models in collaboration with the pilots' ecosystem to guarantee both the long-term sustainability of the project but also enabling fast replication in other follower regions. The BMs will follow a traditional Business Model Canvas approach, tailored on the different regions' specific challenges and customised SIPs enabling the pilots success but also allowing EU-wide replication through the standardisation of some common replicable features. The BMs will be based on specific features for securing success, as shown in the following table they will be:

Figure 3 Key features of innovative Business Models

Furthermore, during the course of the project there will be a second Open Call for follower micro-pilots in other regions. This will enable the testing of the SIPs, methodologies and knowledge developed in SMART ERA, tailored in new scenarios with different socio-economic challenges, thus actually supporting pilot replication, providing a foundation for continued scaling efforts post-project. For the carrying on of this process a Selection Committee will be established, composed by the pilot orchestrators, responsible for the supervision of the whole process¹.

3.1.2. Technology Upscaling and Commercialisation

SMART ERA is advancing the maturity of the integrated tools and technologies within the SIPs; they are expected to reach high maturity by the end of the project. This indicates that following the project end, additional research and development will be required to bring these technologies to higher TRLs, enabling full commercial exploitation. Furthermore, in order to secure the long-term utilisation and further development of the integrated technologies, there will be a strong focus on the sustainability and update of the tools and solutions upscaled. The relative owners responsible for the continuous utilisation and update of the technologies after the project end, will be defined later in the project.

Exploitation activities will detail the strategies to achieve this upscaling, focusing on the following key areas:

- **Identification of further research needs:** pinpoint specific areas that require further research and development to optimise the technologies developed and ensure their full readiness for commercial deployment.
- **Resource and capital evaluation:** assess the necessary human and financial resources required for the upscaling process, ensuring that all elements are in place for an effective TRL upscaling.
- **Assessment of financing mechanisms:** explore and identify potential funding sources, including national and regional programs (e.g., COMET), internal funds, crowdfunding, and commissioned research from interested stakeholders. This will ensure that the necessary financial support is secured for the upscaling activities.
- **Planning for further demonstrations:** organise and execute additional demonstration activities with the help of pilot leaders, winners of the Open Calls, and other contacts established during dissemination and communication activities. These demonstrations will provide practical evidence of the technology's capabilities and readiness for broader deployment.
- **Development of business models and commercial strategies:** formulate robust business models and commercial strategies to guide the market introduction of the upscaled technologies. These strategies will ensure that the technologies are not only technically viable but also commercially attractive.

¹ Each financial support to third parties (FSTP) project will be expected to include exploitation plans in their final reporting documentation.

The market potential and opportunities will steer the TRL upscaling process to ensure that post-project research and development efforts align with regulatory requirements and reflect market demands.

The commercial exploitation strategy for SMART ERA ensures the market viability and sustainability of the developed solutions. This strategy is inevitably tied to the technology upscaling that sets the ground to make the solutions reach full market potential.

A potential pathway for seeking commercial exploitation could be through the development and maintenance of the technological solutions integrated in the SIPs. Thus, involving the pilots as the initial users and customers of these solutions at discounted rates. Following the technology upscaling to TRL 9, there could be evaluation of potential commercialisation and update of offering portfolio to other clients.

3.1.3. Pilot sustainability and service improvement

The exploitation strategy for pilot sustainability in SMART ERA focuses on ensuring the long-term viability and maintenance of the implemented solutions. This includes securing continuous funding to support the ongoing operations and securing the continuity of the SIPs through regular maintenance, and timely updates to keep the systems efficient and effective. Additionally, there is a need to foresee adaptability of the pilots, allowing solutions to evolve in response to changing environments and emerging needs in rural communities.

Furthermore, the improvement and upscaling of services post-project will directly contribute to the sustainability of solutions. This involves expanding target users by reaching different types of target segments and geographic areas, as well as adding new functionalities. By enhancing and broadening the scope of the services, SMART ERA ensures that the benefits are sustained and upscaled over time, fostering continued innovation and impact in rural development.

Examples of main post-project evolutions can be:

- **Tourism** products for local travel agency offerings and related marketing and promotional plans;
- **Policy recommendations** integrated into provincial/regional programming to replicate results in other rural areas;
- Promotion of **public discussions** among village residents in the local municipalities;
- Update of **regional and city strategies** and support SIPs adoption by residents and SMEs.

3.1.4. Academic and Research Exploitation

This strategy leverages SMART ERA's outcomes for academic and research advancements. The academic and RTO partners will integrate project findings into ongoing and future research projects, and publications, disseminating knowledge on smart

assessment tools and social innovations in rural areas. This will also result in the utilisation of project's findings to enhance their academic offering, thus developing new PhD grants, courses, and project proposals based on SMART ERA outcomes to enhance education and foster further research. This approach will contribute to the academic community's understanding of smart rural development and promote continued innovation in the field.

3.1.5. Third party exploitation

The development of solutions and services within SMART ERA will unlock potential for third parties, such as local businesses and service providers, to enhance their operations, develop new services, and enter new markets. The Final Exploitation Plan will detail specific strategies to facilitate further adoption post-project, thus ensuring broad awareness and engagement with SMART ERA innovations, directly benefiting local service and business development. By fostering local innovation and continuous improvement, SMART ERA aims to create a sustainable impact on rural communities, driving long-term economic growth and enhanced service quality.

4. Conclusions

This Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results outlines the comprehensive PCDE strategy for SMART ERA.

Partners can utilise this document to synchronise their local communication activities with the overall project strategy, as it includes visual and content guidelines. Furthermore, it provides an overview of the primary tools and channels to be used for disseminating project outcomes, as well as the monitoring strategy that will be implemented. The channels and formats described in this deliverable aim to ensure awareness, engagement, and uptake among professional stakeholders and the general public. Their effectiveness and reach will be regularly evaluated, allowing the project to fine-tune its content and dissemination strategy over time. In M24, the updated Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results will be delivered (D7.5).

This document also serves as the basis for the exploitation strategy, beginning with the initial identification of KERs and stakeholder groups. It provides partners with the methodology that will be used to develop both joint and individual exploitation strategies, and outlines the steps needed to ensure effective and sustainable exploitation of project results.

Throughout the project's duration, this deliverable will be updated to refine the strategy. At the project's conclusion, the exploitation strategy will be consolidated, offering a comprehensive view of exploitation approaches and target segments in the Final Exploitation Plan (D7.9, M48).